

WP5 - Getting actors to act: dissemination, exploitation and communication

DigitAF

DIGITAF Target groups	Policy-makers, at regional, national and European levels	Practitioners (e.g. farmers, landowners, foresters)	Beneficiaries of AF products and services
Why this group of actors?	"I need to find solutions to meet SDGs and European Green Deal targets, and I want to know the impact the CAP"	"I believe we have to move to sustainable agriculture so I want to try something new and see a growing potential	"I am looking for new options to create carbon credits and I am preparing our story on biodiversity credits." "
What are their needs?			

Mapping of AF stakeholders

Project name	DigitAF (101059794)
Work-package	5: Getting actors to act: dissemination, exploitation and communication
Deliverable	Deliverable 5.4: Mapping of AF stakeholders
Date of report	28/06/2023
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DigitAF project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N°101059794. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Research Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are target by DigitAF are:

- **Policy actors:** policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- **Practitioners:** farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- **Beneficiaries of AF products and services:** stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for the communication about the project and dissemination to all three stakeholders' groups. It contains the creation of three buyer personas representing the three stakeholders groups and more specifically:

- **Buyer persona “Policy actor Agnes”:** represents policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels
- **Buyer persona “Practitioner Jan”:** represents farmers and landowners and, by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems
- **Buyer persona “Beneficiary Carolina”:** represents stakeholders in the value chain and notably wholesalers, retailers, organizations trading carbon sequestration and biodiversity.

A buyer persona is a fictional representation of an ideal customer that is created by businesses to better understand their target audience. It is a detailed profile that describes the characteristics, behaviours, needs, motivations, and demographics of a specific segment of customers.

The three buyer personas will help DigitAF to target communication with precision: relevant contents on the right channel and in the right tone for each target group.

2 Creation of a buyer persona

Each buyer persona has been created with the elaborations of six sections and notably:

2.1 Buyer persona profile

This first section makes the profile “human” in order to refer to it as a real individual and remember it easily. This section specifies: name, age, marital status, job/function, role, education, size of organization, responsibilities, information sources, drivers

2.2 Direct need

Why does the Buyer Persona look for information on Agroforestry and possibly digital tools? This will help us tailor the information disseminated on the website as well as fine-tune the website to come highest on keyword searches made by this group of actors. It triggers actors to look for a solution in a specific moment and it is the first step in developing actors' trust in DigitAF.

2.3 Success factors

What does the Buyer Persona expect from an organization that can help with the transition to agroforestry? This will allow us to target communication on subjects most relevant to the target group. This information will be updated with the data recently acquired in the Living Labs (cf deliverable 4.1).

2.4 Possible barriers

Which barriers does the Buyer Persona see regarding research/innovation consortia, and in particular DigitAF? this will enable us to identify the pitfalls to avoid, anticipating target groups' questions and concerns with accurate answers.

2.5 Decision criteria

What are vital criteria for the Buyer Persona to trust DigitAF and the tools? This will help us keep emphasize the relevant features of the tools developed/improved during the project when communicating about them making DigitAF the right entity to deliver the benefits the target groups want.

2.6 Motto & Answer

What is the motto of the Buyer Persona and what is DigitAF's answer. This will help us formulate the communication of our results so that they have the strongest impact on each of our target groups.

3 Buyer Persona "Policy actor Agnes"

Summary

Ms. Agnes Frere worked as a farmer in Brittany and was active as a member of the council and parliament. In the Assemblée nationale, she was an advocate for the interests of farmers, who was critical of restrictions imposed on agriculture. In the European Parliament, Agnes is a member of the Committees on Agriculture and Rural Development and on Fisheries.

Agnes represents policymakers and administrations concerned with applying Agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of Agroforestry.

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
	Name	Agnes Frere (46)	Marital Status	Married 2 kids	
	Function	Member of the Committees on Agriculture and Rural Development	Role	Policy maker	
	Education	Masters	Size of organization	EU parliament	

Responsibilities		Information sources
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The operation and development of the Common Agricultural Policy Rural development (including the activities of the relevant financial instruments) Legislation on veterinary and plant-health matters, animal feeding provided such measures are not intended to protect against risks to human health Animal husbandry and welfare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvements in the quality of agricultural products Supplies of raw materials for agriculture The Community Plant Variety Office Develop a sustainability budget Work with various departments, officials, and party members, as well as the public opinion Participate in meetings with leadership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peers Team & Political party members News sources like CNN, The Guardian, Financial Times Google
		Drivers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Her own past experience as a farmer Happy and healthy family life Respect from the people around her Contributing to a better future

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
Why is Agnes looking for agroforestry and related topics?					
					<p>“I believe we have to move to sustainable agriculture.”</p> <p>Agnes knows the difficulties faced by her family farm in terms for resilience to climate change effects. The economic, political and environmental instability requires sustainable agricultural practices and food systems: how to implement them also depends on the AGRI Committee.</p>
					<p>“I want farmers to use eco-schemes to mitigate climate change and protect the environment.”</p> <p>Eco-schemes are one of the most important instruments of the new CAP. Agnes knows the importance of giving incentives to farmers in order to support the transition to sustainable agriculture. Since agroforestry is one of the four flagships of the Farm to Fork Strategy, Agnes wants to know how it is widespread in Europe.</p>
					<p>“I need to find solutions to meet SDGs and European Green Deal targets”</p> <p>Ambitious goals need to be achieved by 2030 both at international level (SDG) and at European level (European Green Deal). Agriculture-related targets have the highest priority for Agnes’.</p>
					<p>“I want to know the impact the Common Agricultural Policy”</p> <p>As Member of the AGRI Committee, Agnes feels responsible for the performance of the new CAP.</p>

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What does Agnes expects from an organization that can help transition to agroforestry?					
“They should be able to prove that AF is impactful also in Europe.”			“They should be able to prove that AF is profitable for farmers.”		
Agnes doubts the impact of agroforestry in Europe because most of the initiatives are located in the Global South.			Although environmental and biodiversity benefits are important, Agnes knows that the economic resilience of farmers is crucial. Agroforestry practices should prove a positive impact on crop yields and profits.		
“They should be able to prove that AF practices can be effectively monitored.”			“They should give added value to the European agroforestry framework.”		
Agnes is responsible for the operation and development of the CAP. The monitoring of results achieved by agroforestry systems should help her to meet the KPIs established to assess the performance of the CAP.			Agnes is looking for organizations able to help her understand what she does not know about agroforestry and more specifically about the digital tools available to farmers.		

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
Which negative expectations does Agnes have regarding such an organization and DigitAF in specific?					
“I’ve never heard of DigitAF.”			“They are a bit too scientific.”		
Even if it is an EU funded project, Agnes does not know anything about it and wants to inquire into the consortium to check the reliability.			Agnes works together famers, political parties and EU departments. DigitAF seems to be a project more focused on research activities using a language hard to understand outside the scientific community.		
“There is no evidence.”			“I am already working with a competitor.”		
The project is in an early phase and Agnes cannot have information on where the European policies have the highest impact			Within Agnes’ team, there is already a working relationship with a group of organizations with experience in agroforestry. She does not see what the DigitAF consortium can do better.		

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What are vital criteria for Agnes to follow DigitAF?					
“It is a EU funded project”			“The consortium includes lots of reliable and experienced partners.”		
The project passed the evaluation process imposed by the European Commission and therefore is coherent with EU principles and objectives.			Agnes trusts reliable names with experience in agroforestry and in EU funded projects.		
“They have a good project plan with clear milestones.”			“DigitAF increases knowledge about agroforestry.”		
DigitAF’s team is professional with the intake and works following a project plan with clear milestones and deliverables.			Agnes finds useful that DigitAF synthesize AF policies across Europe and work with farmer groups and CAP Management Agencies to improve the new CAP.		
“Project implementation involves different European countries.”					
Agnes sees a huge benefit in the fact that DigitAF involves different countries in Europe and most of all regarding the Living Labs.					

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What is Agnes motto and what is our answer?					
Motto of Agnes			The proposition		
I want to partner with a consortium that supports me in understanding and enhancing the role of agroforestry in agricultural, environmental and climate policies to meet SDG and EU Green Deal targets. They have to be reliable, professional and experienced. I want sustainable agriculture be a key driver in the new CAP and I want to identify methods to support farmers profitability.			DigitAF provides digital tools to support policy actors in understanding and enhancing the role of agroforestry in agricultural, environmental and climate policies. The consortium composed by 26 experienced partners (RTOs, Universities, SMEs, Cooperatives & NGOs) will help policy makers design more efficient policies and measure the environmental impact and performance of agroforestry systems at a regional level.		

4 Buyer Persona “Practitioner Jan”

Summary

Jan Müller is the third generation of farmers and sees himself as an entrepreneur. When he decided to be his father's successor, he went to college and uni. His father still works at the farm and helps Jan where needed.

Although the agricultural industry is a fairly conservative, Jan wants to change his way of producing to a nature-based agroforestry system.

Jan represents farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
	Name	Jan Müller (34)		Company	family business
	Function	farmer		Role	owner and decision maker
	Education	bachelor or master		Size of organization	80 - 150 hectares, above 120 hectares they have a staff

Responsibilities	Targets	Information sources
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainably managing the land. Keeping a profitable business. Plant, fertilize, cultivate, spray, irrigate and harvest crops. Feed and tend livestock and poultry. Selling crops to one or more off-takers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving the quality of his product Reducing costs. Improving profit. Improving agricultural output (crop per unit). Thinking about new changes/new crops/new markets. Becoming measurably more sustainable. (Getting a eco-certificate) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agrarheute, www.agrarheute.com Land und forst, print magazine Agrartechnik, print magazine Google Facebook and Youtube, (he loves GoPro movies from colleagues) recommendations from network

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
Why is Jan looking for agroforestry and related topics?					
“I believe we have to move to sustainable agriculture.”			“I hear about agroforestry in the media and I’d like to learn about it.”		
Jan is a third generation farmer. He has seen the decline in biodiversity during his life. He believes it’s time to change this.			Jan follows the news and hears more and more about agroforestry practices. He wants to understand the benefits AND the challenges. “I need to know how to manage trees.”		
“My kids are embarrassed about my traditional farming practices.”			“I see a decline in yield and quality.”		
Jan’s two daughters complain about all the ‘poison’ he is using on his land. They are talking into him every day. To make a good impression, he starts to look for information so he can answer them.			With the changed weather conditions, wet spring when seeding - dry summer when growing, Jan’s financial results are under pressure. He wants to understand how he can change the tide.		
“I want to try something new and see a growing potential.”			“The increasing cost of inputs makes traditional farming less profitable.”		
Jan is following the trends and sees an opportunity to sell for a premium price.			Jan knows the current natural nutrient level in his field is low and that he is depending on fertilizers to grow his crops. This is worrying him as he sees rising prices.		

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What does Jan expect from an organization that can help transition to agroforestry?					
“They must think as a farmer.”			“They must be able to explain why I should make the transition in all transparency.”		
Jan has seen quite some advisers in the past and they all pretend to know what is happening on Jan’s farm. Whoever tells him what to do and how to make profit, is already dismissed.			The organization who helps him with the transition should be able to present all cons and pros and not only the pros.		
“They must be able to support me for a longer period.”			“They must speak my language.”		
Jan doesn’t like adviser who never return a call after the deal is done. He looks for a transition partner for the long run.			Jan is German and prefers to speak German. When there eis important information, he likes to see that in German.		
“They must be affordable.”			“They must be independent.”		
Sometimes the cost for advise exceeds the net profit. This is not what Jan is looking for.			Jan has to be certain that the organization or project is not financed by another organization who benefits from the advice.		

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
Which negative expectations does Jan have regarding such an organization and DigitAF in specific?					
“I’ve never heard of DigitAF.”			“I am a farmer, not a test case.”		
Jan is a bit averse of the word Digital and need assurance that will have tools that he can actually use. “Who else is using this?”			Jan doesn't want to test new software. He has a farm to run. The tools provided must work and not require constant updating.		
“They are a bit too scientific.”			“I need to understand the implications of Agroforestry for my farm.”		
Jan works with professionals and is afraid DigitAF might not be in touch with the reality in the field.			Jan is uncertain what the best options are for his type of farm and not sure whether a tool will help him with that. He believes his land is too specific for a reliable digital tool advice.		
“I don’t understand where this data is coming from.”					
Jan does not trust the tool outputs. “Where is the data coming from and has it actually been checked.”					

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What are vital criteria for Jan to follow DigitAF and use the tools?					
“I know the organizations and farms they work with.”			“They show real situations.”		
Jan trusts reliable names in the field. In case leading companies are working with DigitAF, he dares to do the same.			Impressive projects and amazing results are essential to Jan. He wants to see the full potential of DigitAF before she makes a decision.		
“They answer my questions.”			“There are real people behind DigitAF.”		
Jan finds the information about agroforestry and DigitAF complete. Also because the site provides links to other sources.			They reply to Jan's email.		
“It’s funded by the EU.”			“The look and feel is appealing to him as a farmer.”		
Jan finds it comforting to know that the project is supported by EU money. It means there is no commercial entity behind that will ultimately charge him for using the tools.			The communication is at a level in wording and visuals that speaks to Jan as a farmer.		

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What is Jan motto and what is our answer?					
Motto of Jan			The proposition		
I want to be supported by an organization that helps me in a transition to more sustainable practices which also let me enhance crop yields and quality. They have to be supportive, transparent and affordable. They have to understand my needs as a farmer and the context in which I live and work. I already heard about agroforestry but I want to know about all the benefits and challenges that will impact my farm before starting any transition.			DigitAF offers free and user-friendly digital tools that are previously tested on six Living Labs set up in six different countries. DigitAF partners have direct experience in working with farmers and they understand farmers needs and challenges in order to let them make informed decisions regarding agroforestry systems. DigitAF supports farmers to develop business plans to improve the value and marketability of agroforestry products and services in order to show profitability beyond environmental benefits.		

5 Buyer Persona “Beneficiary Carolina”

Summary

Carolina Romano had a career in wholesale but after a short sabbatical, she decided to change jobs and use her negotiation skills for a better purpose. She became a Carbon Portfolio Manager of a Medium sized Carbon trader. She oversees a portfolio of carbon credits, including monitoring performance, assessing risks, and optimizing investments. She makes strategic decisions to maximize returns and minimize environmental impact.

Carolina represents the beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organizations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity.

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
	Name	Carolina Romano (29)	Marital Status	Single	
	Function	Carbon Portfolio Manager	Role	Decision maker	
	Education	Masters	Size of organization	12 people	

Responsibilities	Information sources
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managing a portfolio of carbon credits or offsets. Monitoring and analyzing the performance of existing carbon assets Evaluating risks and opportunities, and making informed investment decisions. Setting investment goals, and determining allocation strategies Identifying opportunities for diversification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team members News sources like CNN, The Guardian, Financial Times, Google
	Drivers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Her vision on the environment Being at ease with inner self Respect from the people around her

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
Why is Carolina looking for agroforestry and related topics?					
	“I am looking for new options to create carbon credits.”				“I am preparing our story on biodiversity credits.”
	Carolina faces the same challenge every day; “Where to generate carbon credits?” Forests are scarce and land ownership is a difficult topic. agroforestry farmers might be a solution.				Besides Carbon Credits, Carolina is preparing Biodiversity Credits as a new item to ‘sell’ to her customers.
	“I personally believe we have to move to sustainable agriculture.”				“I want to better understand the impact of agroforestry.”
	Carolina also has a personal believe that current monoculture is threatening nature. For her agroforestry is a possible alternative.				Carolina’s goal is to drive positive impact. Her company is being closely watched by journalists and consumers, and needs solid reports to prove her work has positive impact on social, economic and environmental level.

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What does Carolina expect from an organization that can help transition to agroforestry?					
"They must prove Agroforestry sequesters carbon."		"They must be able to show the positive impact on nature."			
The true measurable impact of agroforestry is crucial for Carolina. Hollow promises might become an issue in the future.		Carolina needs to be able to explain in a easy to understand story the positive impact of agroforestry on its surrounding.			
"They must be independent."		"They must use reliable tools to measure the sequestration."			
Carolina has to be certain that the organization or project is not financed by another organization who benefits from the advice.		There are so many way to count the carbon sequestered, even within Carolina's team there is a debate on the topic. The company to work with has to use the best tools.			

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
Which negative expectations does Carolina have regarding agroforestry and DigitAF?					
"I've never heard of DigitAF."		"It's too scientific."			
Carolina doesn't like the risk of losing her stature over an organization she has never heard of before. She rather plays safe with the usual suspects.		Carolina needs a simple story but perceives DigitAF as a bunch of scientists using complicated language. She can't compile a story from the website.			
"What are the expected results?"		"There are too many partners."			
Carolina needs clear and proven impact numbers, preferably by the hectare. On the website she can't find one matching answer.		The amount of partners scares Carolina. "Who to point at if anything turns out to be 'wrong'?"			
"Does agroforestry really improve the environment?"		"How legitimate is the information that the digital tools for agroforestry generate?"			
At some point of the customer journey Carolina can have second thoughts. Does nature really benefit and are the examples not too small to have any impact?		Who is testing the tests? Carolina would like to be ensured that the data generates is accurate.			

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What are vital criteria for Carolina to follow DigitAF?					
“DigitAF provides the information I need in plain English.”			“The tools have to be mainstream.”		
Carolina trusts reliable names in the field. In case leading companies are working with DigitAF, she dares to do the same.			Carolina trusts reliable names in the field. Only if leading companies are working with DigitAF tools, she dares to do the same.		
“I dare to share the information they provide on social media.”			“I must be able to understand the interface.”		
Carolina wants to share information about her work on social media every now and then to inspire her clients in her network. DigitAF publishes nice story that she dares to share.			The company where Carolina works is already using some tools for measuring and predicting. Any new tool has to feel and work the same.		
“There are multiple examples in the EU that proves agroforestry is a good solution.”					
Carolina is looking for visual examples that is backed up by digital tools so she can refer to those when a clients ask for it.					

Buyer persona profile	Direct need	Success factors	Possible barriers	Decision criteria	Motto & Answer
What is Carolina motto and what is our answer?					
Motto of Carolina			The proposition		
I want to partner with an organization that helps to find new options to create carbon credits. They have to provide reliable and user-friendly digital tools I can share with my clients and that let me measure and predict carbon sequestration in an accurate way. I know about benefits of agroforestry in terms of carbon sequestration but I also need to know if the impact is real and measurable.			DigitAF helps actors to identify and measure economic, environmental and social performances of agroforestry. DigitAF verifies the effect of agroforestry on net greenhouse emission, carbon sequestration within existing carbon frameworks and soil health. DigitAF proves the impact of agroforestry in terms of carbon sequestration by testing new and existing tools on six Living Labs set up within the project.		

6 Acknowledgements

The DigitAF project (Grant Agreement N° 101059794) is co-funded by the European Commission, European Research Agency, within the Horizon Europe programme, Cluster 6: “Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment”. The views and opinions expressed in this report are purely those of the writers and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.